

Special Relativistic Considerations from $dv/dt = \text{grad}(vv/2) + v \times \text{grad} \times v$?

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In (1) it is suggested that one may develop special relativity from the conservation of acceleration and, in particular, the math identity: $dv/dt = dv/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(vv/2) - v \times \text{grad} \times v$ is used.

In this note, we point out that one may multiply the identity by m_0 and obtain a nonrelativistic expression involving p and kinetic energy $= .5m_0v^2$. We point out that this nonrelativistic expression seems to also hold for nonrelativistic electromagnetism if one considers two point charges at rest held a certain distance apart if one associates $d(m_0v)/dt$ and $v \times$ with a particle and the nonrelativistic energy with $-phi$ and $\text{grad} \times p$ with $\text{grad} \times (-A)$ and $dp/dt \text{ partial}$ with $dA/dt \text{ partial}$. At this point, this may appear as a curiosity.

We then note that if one uses a Galilean transformation and sets $v(\text{particle}) = 0$, there is still phi and A , but the identity would be $d(m_0v)/dt = dA/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(phi)$. If the right hand side is supposed to represent force, the vector portion in the x direction, for a charge moving in the x direction, has a weight different from y and z . One, however, requires a vector to lie along $r(\text{vector})$, i.e. not be weight. This suggests that phi at rest does not transform as $phi(x-vt, y, z)$, but rather as $phi(g(v)(x-vt), y, z)$ where the form $dA/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(phi)$ shows that $g(v)$ must be $1/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ where c is a number with units of velocity. (It may later be shown that this is the speed of light in a vacuum.)

Velocity Identity and Relationship to Nonrelativistic Momentum and Energy

One may write: $dv/dt = dv/dt \text{ partial} + v \cdot \text{grad} \times v$ ((1))

It may be shown that this is equivalent to: $dv/dt = dv/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(vv/2) - v \times \text{grad} \times v$ ((2))
i.e.

$$v_j d_i v_j - e_{ijk} v_j e_{klm} d_l v_m = v_j d_i v_j - (d_{il}d_{jm}) - d_{im}d_{jl}) v_j d_l v_m = v_j d_j v_i \quad ((3))$$

Here $d_i = d/dx_i \text{ partial}$, d_{il} is the Kronecker delta for i, l and e_{ijk} , the Levi-Civita symbol.

((3)) is a math identity, but one may notice that if one multiplies by m_0 , rest mass, one has a nonrelativistic energy-momentum-acceleration identity:

$$dp/dt = dp/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(\text{kinetic energy}) - v \times \text{grad} \times p \quad ((4))$$

One may note that ((4)) is of the exact form as the Lorentz force equation if kinetic energy is associated with minus electrostatic potential energy phi and p in $dp/dt \text{ partial}$ and $\text{grad} \times p$ with $-dA/dt \text{ partial}$ and $-\text{grad} \times A$. $v \times$ is then associated with a second particle's velocity and dp/dt with the change in momentum of this second particle.

One may consider that this link with the Lorentz force equation is a coincidence. On the other hand, one may suggest that one cannot distinguish between different kinds of energy and momenta and so there may be nothing wrong with ((4)) matching the Lorentz equation form. It is interesting, however, that the Lorentz form:

$$dp/dt = -q dA/dt \text{ partial} - \text{grad}(\phi) q + qv \times \text{grad} \times A \quad ((5))$$

holds both relativistically and nonrelativistically, while ((4)) holds in the p, KE form, nonrelativistically.

Given that ((4)), which follows from a math identity, but applies to nonrelativistic KE matches the Lorentz force equation ((5)), let us assume that one does not know about special relativity. For example, special relativity was developed about 1905 while ((5)) was formally written by Lorentz by 1895, but may have been known by Maxwell as early as 1865. If that is the case, is it possible to suggest that there is something wrong with ((5)) if one only has a Galilean transformation?

**Problem with a Galilean Transformation and
 $dp/dt = -q dA/dt \text{ partial} - \text{grad}(\phi) q + qv \times \text{grad} \times A$**

dp/dt equals force which should be measurable along a radius vector. Consider a Galilean transformation: $x'' \rightarrow x-vt$, $y'' \rightarrow y$ and $z'' \rightarrow z$. Here ("") denotes the rest (nonmotion frame of a source charge.) In such a case, if v is along the x axis, then $qv \times \text{grad} \times A$ has no x component, while $dA/dt \text{ partial}$ is all x component. Then:

$$-dA/dt \text{ partial} - \text{grad}(\phi) \text{ (x component)} = -(-vv + 1) d/dx(\phi) \quad ((6))$$

Here $A = \phi/v$ as A is taken to be the momentum of a moving ϕ . If one treats $qv \times \text{grad} \times A$ as a separate force because it depends on v of a second particle, then the two pieces which do not depend on v of the second particle should have a vector of the form of (x,y,z) , but ((6)) shows that the x -component is skewed.

$$d\phi/dy \rightarrow y \text{ function}(r) \text{ and } d\phi/dz = z \text{ function}(r) \text{ while the } x \text{ component is } (vv+1) \text{ function}(r) \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Thus, to have an } (x,y,z) \text{ vector one requires that } x'' \rightarrow g(v)(x-vt) \text{ where } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}. \quad ((8))$$

Here c is introduced as a constant with units of speed. (It may be shown independently that c is the speed of light in a vacuum.)

The reason that one has $g(v)g(v)$ from $d\phi/dx$ is that one has a function of r where:

$$R = \sqrt{g(v)g(v)(x-vt)(x-vt) + yy + zz} \quad ((9))$$

Thus, d/dx brings back $g(v)g(v)$, but only one factor of $(x-vt)$. Thus, it seems that going from a rest frame to a moving one, with motion in the x direction, requires $x'' \rightarrow g(v) (x-vt)$.

This conclusion could have been reached using only the Lorentz force equation ((5)) without any recourse to ((4)), the velocity identity which may be altered to create a nonrelativistic energy-momentum identity which matches the nonrelativistic Lorentz force equation.

Given, however, the link between the math identity and nonrelativistic KE ((4)) and ((5)), if ((5)) implies a different transformation from a Galilean for $x'' \rightarrow$ in the moving frame, one may consider this transformation applying to ϕ and A as well. For instance, in the rest frame, one has only ϕ'' , but as seen in the moving frame, there is ϕ and A , where A is proportional to ϕ v . If ϕ and A are associated with a transformation different from the Galilean, one would expect that a similar conclusion holds for E and p for a moving non-charged particle.

In particular, $x'' \rightarrow g(v) (x-vt)$ is consistent with:

$$\begin{aligned} |x| &= |g \ gv| |x''| \quad ((10)) \\ |t| &= |gv \ g| |t''| \end{aligned}$$

If one considers $(0, \phi'')$ in the rest frame, then:

$\Phi = g \phi''$ and $A = v \ g \ \phi''$ i.e. momentum appears naturally from such a transformation, but there is an extra factor of g . One could also apply this to $(0, m_0) \rightarrow (m_0 \ g \ v, m_0 \ g)$. This implies that rest mass becomes $m_0 \ g \ c^2$ as energy when the particle moves.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that there exists a math identity: $dv/dt = dv/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(vv/2) - v \times \text{grad} \times v$. In the nonrelativistic case, this may be multiplied by m_0 to yield a nonrelativistic energy-momentum-acceleration equation: $dp/dt = dp/dt \text{ partial} + \text{grad}(\text{kinetic energy}) + v \times \text{grad} \times p$. This equation mimics the Lorentz force equation of electromagnetism (which may also be considered in a nonrelativistic limit) if one associates KE with $-\phi$ (electrostatic potential) and p in $dp/dt \text{ partial}$ and $\text{grad} \times p$ with $-A$. dp/dt and $v \times$ apply to a second particle. If one notes that $v \times \text{grad} \times A$ is zero for $v=0$, then $-\text{grad} \phi - dA/dt \text{ partial}$ seem to be grouped together. Taking a particle at rest with ϕ'' and using a Galilean transformation $x'' \rightarrow x-vt$ with x'' denoting the rest frame, a problem arises. One wishes the $-\text{grad} \phi - dA/dt \text{ partial}$ force to be along a vector r , i.e. (x,y,z) , but it is $((1-vv/cc)x, y,z)$. (Here c is a constant with units of speed which may independently be shown to be the speed of light in a vacuum.) This suggests that $x'' \rightarrow g(v) (x-vt)$ because $r'' = \sqrt{x''^2 + y''^2 + z''^2}$. $d/dx \text{ ph}(r = \sqrt{g^2(x-vt)^2 + y^2 + z^2})$ yields $gg(x-vt)$ function(r). Thus: $g=1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$.

If a transformation different from the Galilean applies to $x'' \rightarrow g(x-vt)$, one may consider the matrix which yields this transformation ((11)) and also apply it to $(0, \phi'')$ to find $(v \ g \ \phi'', g$

phi”) which is consistent with the ideas above. Given that phi is energy and was associated with KE in the math identity, then one might also expect that: $(0, m_0 c^2) \rightarrow (p = m_0 v, m_0 c^2)$. In the nonrelativistic limit $m_0 c^2 \rightarrow m_0 c^2 + \frac{1}{2} m_0 v^2$.

References

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